

Designing and Controlling a Hybrid Fuel Cell System for Propelling a Turboprop Aircraft

Author, co-author (Do NOT enter this information. It will be pulled from participant tab in MyTechZone)

Affiliation (Do NOT enter this information. It will be pulled from participant tab in MyTechZone)

Abstract

In the context of aviation sector decarbonization, fuel cell hybrid electric aircrafts are a promising alternative to conventional fuels, presenting opportunities for more sustainable and efficient flight. Hence, the present work is focused on an alternative powertrain architecture, wherein a proton exchange membrane fuel cell system cooperates with a lithium-ion battery to fulfil the electrical power demand of a turboprop-based aircraft. Particularly, a mathematical tool is proposed to evaluate both the components size and performance, while a degradation aware rule-based control strategy guarantees an effective power split between the hybridizing components. Such an energy management approach introduces an idling level and a rate limiter to mitigate degradation associated with start-up/shut-down and transient phases, respectively. Moreover, to have a reliable estimation of the vehicle's fuel economy, while also guaranteeing the correct components dimensioning, the fuel cell system efficiency model accounts for the recent targets on the achievable power density. The methodology has been applied to a realistic mission profile and the validity of the proposed rule-based strategy, which relies on versatile control maps, has been confirmed via benchmarking against dynamic programming results. The use of such a reference optimal controller for validation purposes represented a novelty in the aviation field. Specifically, when considering an electrical degree of hybridization of 0.79, the dynamic programming outputs a fuel consumption 2% lower than the rule-based strategy, ensuring the effectiveness of the latter.

Introduction

The current international objective is to reduce global greenhouse gas emissions. Particularly, it is estimated that 20 [%] of global CO₂ emissions come from the transportation sector [1]. A significant percentage of this figure is attributable to aviation [2], therefore governments countermeasures are needed (i.e., European Green Deal). To tackle these issues, several projects are currently focused on promoting alternative aircraft powertrain propulsion systems. Nevertheless, the development of a fully electric aircraft solely powered by batteries presents significant challenges, primarily due to the low specific energy of these devices. Compounding this challenge is the stringent criteria set by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) for commercial aircraft. These requirements demand the capability to ensure 45 minutes reserve under instrument conditions or at night flight for all fixed wing aircraft [3]. In case of a fully electric aircraft, such constraints are met considering an additional 30 [%] of remaining stored energy [4], which implies significant innovation in

battery technology and aircraft design in order not to exceed the dimensional constraints.

Hence, a hybrid electric aircraft emerges as a potential solution to mitigate these challenges. In this configuration, a fuel cell system and a battery are combined to fulfil the mission, as shown in Figure 2. Specifically, fuel cells have an energy density higher than batteries but suffer under fluctuating power conditions, owing to the system efficiency reduced at rated power. The most suitable fuel cell technology to be used for aviation is the proton-exchange membrane, mainly due to the high power-to-mass ratio and resulting limited impact on the aircraft's maximum take-off mass (MTOM). However, it is pivotal to clarify that the fuel cell stack needs a series of auxiliary components, which have to ensure the proper functioning of the entire system.

Against this background, the proper sizing of the fuel cell system and battery is a critical aspect to contain the MTOM as much as possible. For instance, the work [5] proposed a model for the sizing of a fuel cell system aimed at aircraft applications. The results of the study highlight that the overall weight and size of the fuel cell system are appropriate for small aircraft. Another study [6] focuses on the feasibility of liquid hydrogen tank as energy carrier and cooling agent for small full electric (proton exchange fuel cell and battery without internal combustion engine) aircraft. Nevertheless, the current technological limitations of the proton-exchange membrane fuel cell prevent it from matching the weight-to-power ratio of existing auxiliary power units. The authors of [7] define the optimal requirements, in terms of battery pack sizing and cell technology, for a hybrid electric regional wing-mounted distributed propulsion aircraft. Another research effort aims to offer an optimization-based approach for designing a hybrid propulsive system incorporating two power sources: jet fuel and hydrogen [8]. In 2010, an innovative aircraft, hybridized with a proton-exchange fuel cell power system, underwent demonstrative flights. This system integrated a fuel cell system capable of generating a maximum power output of 40 [kW], also thanks to a battery pack [9]. Several studies concentrate on investigating the performance of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) equipped with a hybrid powertrain, comprising a proton-exchange membrane fuel cell system and a battery. In [10], the impact of temperature variation on UAVs is analyzed, revealing through simulation results, that the UAV model relying solely on the fuel cell as its power source demonstrates the longest endurance. Moreover, a suitable energy management of the fuel cell system plays a key role in both mitigating the failures that can occur and reducing the fuel consumption. The EU-funded HECATE (hybrid electric regional aircraft distribution technologies) project focuses on system weight and power density, as well as on optimized thermal management [11]. An energy management optimization strategy for

hybrid electric aircraft is proposed in [4], where an optimal control strategy to reduce the degradation of the fuel cell system components is detailed. For controlling the fuel cell temperature, thermal management systems are required, which can be optimized for aircraft applications regarding their weight and reliability. Results from the model proposed in [12] indicate that both the hydrogen mass flow and hydrogen inlet temperature should be used to control the fuel cell temperature. Another study also shows that the choice of fuel cell operating temperature has a first-order impact on the total mass of the propulsive system due to the higher cooling requirement of the low temperature fuel cells [8]. The interest in the integration of fuel cells and batteries into aircraft is also confirmed by the development of advanced control strategies guaranteeing the safety and redundancy features characterizing aircrafts operation. Regarding this aspect, a study [13] includes the possibility to charge the battery passively and actively from the fuel cell or by recuperating during flight reducing the required battery size. As there said, this new concept can be adapted to power various kinds of hybrid aircrafts and offers a guideline to long-term all-electric flights, since it is scalable for different aircraft sizes including single-aisle aircrafts.

The present manuscript focuses on the design of the electrical part of a hybrid powertrain for a turboprop-based regional aircraft, in which a proton exchange membrane fuel cell system (PEMFCS) and battery pack (B) are coupled to satisfy the electrical mission load. Specifically, a series-parallel architecture is considered in this work. The parallel connection (mechanical summation) is between the gas turbine (i.e., thermal engine) and electric motor, while, considering only the powertrain electrical part, the B and the PEMFCS constitute a series hybrid configuration (i.e., electrical summation). In this way, battery pack and PEMFCS can satisfy the power demand (P_{dem}) to be met by the powertrain electrical part; eventually, the PEMFCS can recharge the battery.

Based on the aircraft architecture described above, various novel contributions are provided in the manuscript. Particularly, starting from the methodology presented in [14], the PEMFCS efficiency model and rule-based control strategy have been updated according to new technological scenarios presented in the strategic research and innovation agenda of the Clean Hydrogen partnership (CH2E-SRIA) [15]. Moreover, a degradation aware energy management approach is presented that manages transient phases via a rate limiter on the PEMFCS power supply, while frequent start and stop phases are avoided by introducing an idling power.

Furthermore, such an approach was here validated using dynamic programming (DP) that is an optimal control logic widely used in automotive field [16]. The DP routine also includes a boundary line computation method to improve the searching for the optimal solution. The use of DP in the aviation sector hardly finds similar in literature.

The approach described was applied to a realistic electrical load of a regional aircraft.

The remaining part of the article is organized as follows: First, the mathematical models used to size and control the electrical powertrain are presented. Particularly, the PEMFCS and battery models are detailed, along with the blended rule-based control strategy. In the next section, the selected technical parameters of the battery, PEMFCS and hydrogen tank together with the electrical mission power profile are identified. After that, an in-depth analysis of the DP and its mathematical definition are provided. A substantial modification done with respect to [16], due to adaptation for aviation, concerns the choice of the control variable. Finally, results are shown and discussed: firstly, a comparison between the simulations with original and updated control maps is presented, then DP-based validation of the RB control

strategy (integrated with idling power and rate limiter) is described. Moreover, the final section proposes potential future follow-ups.

Methodology

Figure 1. The figure shows a synoptic diagram. The inputs (i.e., design specification, power demand and technological scenario) are provided to the mathematical tool which calculates the fuel economy and powertrain mass and volume. Afterwards, dynamic programming allows the validation of both the control strategy and design architecture.

The methodology presented here is based on the mathematical tool detailed by the authors in [14], which allows for defining off-line the preliminary design of the hybrid aircraft electrical powertrain architecture. On the other hand, the proposed rule-based control strategy is implementable online based on offline decisions.

The mathematical tool presented in Figure 1 requires mission power, design assumptions and technological scenario information as inputs. It is worth noting that the technological scenario is retrieved from CH2E-SRIA (e.g., PEMFCS gravimetric power density, tank gravimetric efficiency to name a few). Thanks to these inputs, the blended control strategy, during the simulation, manages the contribution of both PEMFCS and B to satisfy the P_{dem} . This control strategy is versatile since it can be adapted to different degrees of hybridization through the denormalization and normalization process of the control maps used by the mathematical tool. Moreover, the implemented energy management strategy for the transient and start and stop phases to reduce the degradation of the PEMFCS, represents an additional contribution of the present study. In particular, a rate limiter and an idling on the fuel cell system power are introduced.

The tool outputs the powertrain mass and volume, while estimating the aircraft's fuel economy (FE). The latter is used as benchmark to validate the RB control strategy by means of the DP routine. It is worth mentioning here that the manuscript focuses only on the electrical part of the entire turboprop-based powertrain, which is schematically shown in Figure 2.

It is also worth noting here that the FE calculated is mathematically defined as the ratio between the distance (D) travelled by the aircraft in a typical mission, which requires a certain flight time, and the total consumption of hydrogen (M_{H_2}):

$$FE = \frac{D}{M_{H_2}} \left[\frac{km}{kg} \right] \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. The diagram of the powertrain model is shown. The proton-exchange membrane fuel cell system and battery, through the electrical node, work together with the thermal engine (TE) to meet the power demand. The red box shows the proton-exchange membrane fuel cell system efficiency model. The green box shows the equivalent circuit model of the battery.

Mathematical Models

Herein, the mathematical models needed to size the PEMFCS-battery hybrid unit and related control strategy are described.

Parametric Mass Model

This model is used for estimating the total mass and volume of the electrical part of the powertrain. It requires the definition of the electric motor rated power (P_{EM} [kW]) as well as the nominal size of the PEMFCS. As for the mass, the following contributions are considered:

$$M_{tot} = M_{batt} + M_{PEMFCS} + M_{H_2tank} + M_{H_2} \quad (2)$$

Where M_{tot} [kg] is the total mass of the electrical powertrain, obtained from summing the contributions of the battery (M_{batt} [kg]), fuel cell system (M_{PEMFCS} [kg]), hydrogen storage tank (M_{H_2tank} [kg]) and M_{H_2} . The mass of the battery is calculated by assessing the power of such a device via a power balance at the electrical node that is expressed in the following equation:

$$P_{batt} = \frac{P_{EM}}{0.9} - P_{PEMFCS} \quad (3)$$

Where P_{batt} [kW] is the nominal power of the battery pack and 0.9 is a coefficient that considers the average efficiency of such a device. Therefore, the number of battery cells (N_{BC} [-]) can be estimated through the ratio between the battery pack power and the nominal power related to the single cell (P_{BC}):

$$N_{BC} = \frac{P_{batt}}{P_{BC}} \quad (4)$$

By determining N_{BC} , the total battery mass can be calculated as in the equation (5).

$$M_{batt} = N_{BC} \cdot m_{B,cell} \quad (5)$$

Where $m_{B,cell}$ [kg/cell] is the unit mass of a single cell of the battery pack, which is estimated as a function of the battery cell energy density, as detailed in [14]. On the other hand, the mass of the PEMFCS is carried out according to equation (6), in which $m_{uPEMFCS}$ [kg/kW] is representative of the unit mass:

$$M_{PEMFCS} = P_{PEMFCS} \cdot m_{uPEMFCS} \quad (6)$$

The chosen technological parameters of B and PEMFCS are described in the following Scenario Analysis and Flight Mission Definition Section.

The estimation of M_{H_2tank} depends on the following expression:

$$M_{H_2tank} = \frac{M_{H_2}}{m_{u,tank}} \quad (7)$$

Where $m_{u,tank}$ [kg H_2 /kg $tank$] stands for the needed mass of hydrogen tank for each kg of hydrogen. As for the volume [l] added to the powertrain, the contributions are provided in equation (8):

$$Vol_{tot} = Vol_{batt} + Vol_{PEMFCS} + Vol_{H_2tank} \quad (8)$$

Where Vol_{batt} [l] is the total volume occupied by the battery pack, Vol_{PEMFCS} [l] is the total volume occupied by the PEMFCS and Vol_{H_2tank} [l] is the volume of the hydrogen tank.

The volume of the battery pack is then calculated using the following expression:

$$Vol_{batt} = N_{BC} \cdot Vol_{cell} \quad (9)$$

Where Vol_{cell} [l] is the volume occupied by a single battery cell. The Vol_{PEMFCS} is estimated through equation (10):

$$Vol_{PEMFCS} = \frac{P_{PEMFCS}}{vol_{PEMFCS}} \quad (10)$$

In the equation above, vol_{PEMFCS} is the volumetric power density of the PEMFCS, expressed in [kW/l]. The volume of the hydrogen tank is calculated through the following expression:

$$Vol_{H_2tank} = \frac{M_{H_2}}{vol_{tank}} \quad (11)$$

Where vol_{tank} [kg H_2 /l $tank$] stands for the needed volume of hydrogen tank for each kg of hydrogen consumed.

PEMFCS Efficiency Model

The PEMFCS efficiency has to be evaluated also accounting for the power absorbed by auxiliaries, as is done in the following expression:

$$\eta_{PEMFCS} = \frac{P_{stack} - P_{aux}}{\dot{m}_{H_2} \cdot HHV_{H_2}} = \frac{P_{PEMFCS}}{\dot{m}_{H_2} \cdot HHV_{H_2}} \quad (12)$$

Where HHV_{H_2} is the hydrogen higher heating value, equal to 141.9 [MJ/kg], P_{aux} [kW] is the power needed for auxiliaries, \dot{m}_{H_2} is the mass flow rate of hydrogen, P_{stack} [kW] is related to the power fed by the

fuel cell stack, which, when subtracted of the amount required for the auxiliaries, becomes the net system power (P_{PEMFCS}).

In [14] and [17], a maximum current density (J) of $0,3 \left[\frac{A}{cm^2} \right]$ was considered. Conversely, in the present manuscript, CH2E-SRIA targets have been considered [15], according to which $1 \left[\frac{A}{cm^2} \right]$ is the 2020 target. Since the experimental data available [17], reached only $0,3 \left[\frac{A}{cm^2} \right]$, a predictive model has been here exploited to investigate higher values of J till reaching a maximum cell voltage of about 0,65 [V].

In Figure 3, the comparison between the efficiency curves, derived from the different J, is presented. The highest efficiency, at high J, is reached at low values of PEMFCS normalized power. This suggests modifying the control strategy used in [14] by updating control maps. Indeed, the new efficiency curve affects hydrogen consumption estimation, which is crucial for implementing the approach detailed in the Control Strategy section.

Figure 3. The figure shows the resultant new efficiency curve according to the target CH2E-SRIA [15] $J = 1 \left[\frac{A}{cm^2} \right]$ and that one at $J = 0,3 \left[\frac{A}{cm^2} \right]$.

Battery Model

The PEMFCS is limited by a slow response to power peaks, which can cause the failure of mechanical components of the system. Thus, to achieve a stable power output, the PEMFCS should be coupled with another energy storage system, such as a battery [18]. In this work, the battery is modeled as an open circuit voltage source in series with an internal resistance ($R_{in} [m\Omega]$). R_{in} changes depending on the SOC, and it is different when considering charging or discharging phases. Maps showing the variation of internal resistance and OCV [V] as a function of the battery SOC are derived from [19]. Moreover, it is worth remarking that the battery cell voltage [V] is computed as follows:

$$V_{batt,cell} = OCV - R_{in,cell} \cdot I_{b,cell} \quad (13)$$

Where $I_{b,cell}$ is the current of a single cell [A].

$$P_{batt,cell} = \frac{P_{batt}}{N_{BC}} \quad (14)$$

$$P_{batt,cell} = V_{batt,cell} \cdot I_{b,cell} = OCV \cdot I_{b,cell} - R_{in,cell} \cdot I_{b,cell}^2 \quad (15)$$

Where $P_{batt,cell}$ [kW] is the power of the single cell included in the pack. From equation (15), it is possible to isolate $I_{b,cell}$ as follows:

$$I_{b,cell} = \frac{V_{batt,cell} - \sqrt{V_{batt,cell}^2 - 4 \cdot R_{in,cell} \cdot P_{batt,cell}}}{2 \cdot R_{in,cell}} \quad (16)$$

Where η_{batt} [-] is the battery efficiency. Therefore, it is possible to calculate the instantaneous SOC variation (ΔSOC [%]) in the following way:

$$\Delta SOC = - \frac{\int_{t_0}^{t_f} I_{b,cell} dt}{Q_{tot}} \quad (17)$$

Where Q_{tot} [Ah] is the total capacity of the battery. Moreover, it is worth remarking that the assessment of both battery and PEMFCS nominal power allows defining a DH [%] (equation 18), which is related to the electrical part of the powertrain (see Figure 1).

$$DH = \frac{P_{batt}}{P_{PEMFCS} + P_{batt}} \quad (18)$$

Control Strategy

At the beginning of the mission, the battery SOC is set at 95 [%] to cope with the selected blended energy management strategy. The battery is discharged until the SOC reaches a target value (alias desired final SOC), labelled as SOC_t . As for the PEMFCS side, it is always turned on and, when the mission power exceeds a certain threshold (i.e., during take-off and landing phases), it is forced to operate at the maximum power level to avoid a rapid discharge of the battery. For this reason, the control strategy is said blended. During cruising, when the power request is lower, the SOC decreases and the PEMFCS is switched on exclusively when the SOC_t is achieved, being capable of contributing for both propulsion and battery charging. It is worth pinpointing that the SOC can move between a higher and a lower threshold, which are determined by means of control maps [20] relying on the updated efficiency curve. In such a defined range of SOC, the PEMFCS provides alternatively the power: it recharges the battery up to the higher threshold and it is switched off until the lower threshold is reached. In this way the strategy promotes the optimal integration of battery and PEMFCS. In detail, the control maps are developed in such a way to define: an admissible SOC excursion and the power fed by the PEMFCS as a function of the average mission power demand (\bar{P}_m). The latter is known in advance and is estimated over a given time horizon. This control strategy allows for changing the time horizon without increasing significantly computational effort, thus demonstrating flexibility, unlike strategies such as dynamic programming described later. This flexibility is essential to allow PEMFCS to adapt to the required power variation as quickly as possible, e.g. in case of high degree of hybridization. Moreover, it is worth remarking that SOC excursion (ΔSOC) results from the time, during which the PEMFCS has to be kept switched off ($\Delta t_{PEMFCS-OFF}$ [s]), which is an output of the minimization performed using equations (19) and (20). For the remaining time the PEMFCS is switched on to sustain the charge of the battery.

$$\min[\dot{m}_{H_2}(X, \bar{P}_m)] \quad (19)$$

Where:

$$X = [P_{PEMFCS}, \Delta t_{PEMFCS-OFF}] \quad (20)$$

Particularly, equation (19) minimizes the mass flow rate of hydrogen ($\dot{m}_{H_2} \left[\frac{kg}{s} \right]$) handling the control variables in equation (20). In this context, it should be put attention to the fact that frequent turn on off

shut-downs of the PEMFCS accelerate system degradation [21], due to the occurrence of mechanical stresses that ultimately lead to failure. Specifically, during start-ups and shut-downs, high pressure differences between anode and cathode could take place resulting in high voltage drops and power loss. Specifically, the higher the number of stacks in the system, the higher the necessity of an accurate pressure control [22]. Furthermore, the temperature could overcome rapidly the upper limit of 100 [°C] damaging system components. For these reasons, an idling power level (P_{idl}) is introduced to keep the PEMFCS always active, while a slew rate (SR) is employed to monitor system's dynamics. As for the latter aspect, the PEMFCS power supply is constrained to a variation per second of maximum 10% of the power rating. The selection of such a constraint is supposed to be reasonable according to the findings in [23]. Consequently, the power varies like a ramp.

On the other hand, it is important to consider that the PEMFCS is providing, in idling condition, energy that is not necessary. This consideration leads to selecting a low idling power level that, according to the efficiency curve in Figure 3, is set to 22% of the power rating that corresponds to the best efficiency point.

It is worth remarking here that the aim of such strategy is that of avoiding degrading PEMFCS operating conditions, while a comprehensive overview of the principal degradation mechanisms can be found in [21].

Scenario Analysis and Flight Mission Definition

This Section presents the technological scenarios that have been considered in this work. Specifically, principal parameters for each powertrain component (i.e., battery, PEMFCS and hydrogen tank) are selected. Following [14], the scenario B1DH79 is considered. Specifically, B1 stands for the battery gravimetric energy density of 300 [Wh/kg], while DH refers to the degree of hybridization, here set to 79 [%] depending on the selected 500 kW PEMFCS and 1833 kW battery. These choices derive from the electrical load profile displayed in Figure 4.

Battery

As for this energy storage system, a lithium-ion battery is selected and an energy density nowadays well-established of 300 $\frac{Wh}{kg}$ is considered as fixed value [24]. Such batteries can be relatively cheap and can be put in modules to build larger systems of several hundred [kWh] energy capacity. Today, the development of other Lithium-based battery systems is pushed forward. Lithium-Sulphur and Lithium-Oxygen are two systems, on which research and development are focused. While Sulphur-based systems have reached practical prototype status, oxygen-based systems are still in their infancy. Theoretical specific energy of Lithium-Sulphur system: 2570 [Wh/kg] and of Lithium- Oxygen system: 3500 [Wh/kg] [25].

PEMFCS and Hydrogen Tank

On the other hand, the technology chosen for the fuel cell system is the PEMFC. The choice depends on its safe and reliable operating temperature (30 ~ 100 [°C]) [18], and the high-power density (kW/kg). As for the power density, it is a crucial aspect to reduce the overall mass of the electrical powertrain. In such a work, a PEMFCS gravimetric power density of 2 [kW/kg] has been considered, which is the 2030 target according to the CH2E-SRIA [15]. A key factor which makes PEMFC a desirable choice is the possibility to achieve high

number of operating hours without significant degradation [26]. Another important aspect is the increase of redundancy [27], which is incredibly significant in the aeronautical sector. As a result, a 500 [kW] PEMFCS is selected as fixed value, with $m_{uPEMFCS}$ and vol_{PEMFCS} respectively equal to 0.5 $\frac{kg}{kW}$ [15] and $\frac{1}{0.85} \frac{l}{kW}$ [5]. The above gravimetric and volumetric power density values, which are taken into account in the PEMFCS model-based sizing task (see equations (6) and (10)), also account for the cooling system required for the proper function of the fuel cell stack.

For hydrogen storage, the choice is liquid hydrogen, even if it exhibits some issues, especially related to the boil-off phenomenon [28]. The tank mass and volume depend on the mass of hydrogen contained. Indeed, vol_{tank} and $m_{u,tank}$ are respectively equal to 0,04 $\frac{kg}{l}$ and 0,15 $\frac{kg}{l}$ found in [15].

Flight Mission and Constraints

The flight mission was derived from available data about regional aircraft, and it is the power requested to the electric motor (EM) in Figure 2. The power profile (P_{dem}), which is one input of the mathematical tool, is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The figure shows the electrical power demand considered. The take-off and landing are the more demanding phases exhibiting a request of 2600 kW. During the cruise a constant power is requested. Source 14.

The constraints in terms of mass and volume considered are synthesized in the Table 1 and are coherent with the state of art of the technologies analyzed.

Table 1. The table shows the constraints on the minimum admissible battery state of charge (SOC), the total mass, and the total volume. Source 14.

Constraints	
M_{tot}	3600 [kg]
V_{tot}	3000 [l]
SOC_{min}	$\cong 20\%$

Dynamic Programming

In this Section, dynamic programming is presented as the benchmark for validating the RB control strategy proposed. DP, which is an optimal controller, is widely used in automotive sector that was here adapted to meet specific aviation requirements.

DP Mathematical Definition

DP is an offline control strategy, whose main benefit lies in the possibility of attaining results close to the optimality by relying on Bellman's theory. Researchers also proposed its deployment online, although the time-horizon to be selected to ensure control outcomes be as close as possible to the theoretical offline benchmark may be difficult to determine [29].

The global solution to the optimization problem is constituted by merging sub-optimal solutions relative to a variety of sub-problems. Additionally, such a control scheme allows for handling multiple complex constraints on both states and inputs variables with a low computational burden. DP is only used as benchmark for assessing the goodness of sub-optimal strategies. Indeed, the boundary line allows for reducing the computational points, through which the program searches the best solution. The class of optimal control problems that can be solved using the proposed DP routine [16] can be written as follows:

$$J = M_{H_2}(u(t)) \quad (21)$$

Where M_{H_2} is the cost function to minimize, while u is the control variable (e.g., the power split), which is time dependent. The continuous-time model is expressed in equation (22):

$$\dot{x}(t) = F(x(t), u(t), t) \quad (22)$$

Where x is the state variable of the problem and, in the analyzed case, it corresponds to the SOC, for which an initial condition (x_0) has to be selected (i.e., the battery initial state of charge).

$$x(0) = x_0 \quad (23)$$

The final SOC value is kept into a range whose limit can be:

$$x(t_f) \in [x_{f,min}, x_{f,max}] \quad (24)$$

$$x(t) \in X(t) \in R^n \quad (25)$$

$$x(t) \in U(t) \in R^m \quad (26)$$

Where t_f is referred to final simulation time (end time of the mission). So, the final SOC is imposed and fulfilled by the DP.

The computation of the mass of hydrogen in the equation (21) is made through integration of the equation (27).

$$J = G(x(t_f)) + \int_0^{t_f} \dot{m}_{H_2}(x(t), u(t), t) dt \quad (27)$$

Where G is the penalty term that is useful to make a harder constraint (e.g., on the final SOC to be achieved).

The continuous problem (equation (21)) should be discretized to be solved computationally. So, there is a grid (NxM) whose x-axis is the mission time (N points), and y-axis is the SOC (M points). The computation frequency is 1 [Hz], so it is done every second of the mission profile. As for the range of final SOC, equation (24), the control variable also needs a numerical interval, in which its variation

is admitted. In equation (28) the control variable (u) is indicated, while providing the variation range admitted:

$$u = \frac{P_{PEMFCS}}{P_{PEMFCS_{max}}} \in [0,1] \quad (28)$$

When u is equal to 1 [-], the PEMFCS provides the nominal power, while when u is 0 [-], the PEMFCS is turned off. The values ranging between the upper and lower threshold stand for the partial load conditions. Moreover, it is worth remarking that 61 points are used to discretize the state variable grid, according to [16].

Aviation Adaptation and Implementation

The admitted operating modes, presented in Figure 5, are the hybrid and recharge modes. It is important to note that the battery can be recharged also via the airport's infrastructure (post-driving recharging) but, if this last option is not available, the PEMFCS can recharge the battery by working at its best efficiency condition.

Figure 5. In the hybrid mode (a) both the battery and the proton-exchange membrane fuel cell system provide energy for the propulsion, while in the recharge mode (b), the proton-exchange membrane fuel cell system both recharges the battery and satisfies the mission.

The inputs provided to DP routine are:

- P_{dem} [kW].
- The maximum (0,95 [-]) and minimum (0,15 [-]) SOC. This is due to both reducing the degradation of the battery and always guaranteeing an energy reserve.
- The maximum electric motor power (P_{EM}) [kW].
- The voltage and internal resistance (both in charging and in discharging phases) maps ($OCV(SOC)$, $R_{chg}(SOC)$, $R_{dischg}(SOC)$) [19]. Since the battery model is referred to a single cell, the number of cells of the battery pack (N_{BC}) is

inherited by the mathematical tool in [14] (passage from equation (14) to equation (15)).

- The maximum discharging current of the single battery cell ($I_{b,cell,max}$) imposed as 60 [A]. It is worth remarking that such a value results from the approximation of the following expression:

$$I_{b,cell,max} = C_{rate} \cdot C_{cell} \text{ [A]} \quad (29)$$

Where C_{rate} is 15 $\left[\frac{1}{h}\right]$ and its expression, equation (29) is derived from [30]:

$$C_{rate} = \frac{I_{dischg/chg} \text{ [A]} \left[\frac{1}{h}\right]}{C_{cell} \text{ [Ah]} \left[\frac{1}{h}\right]} \quad (30)$$

In this case study, the selected gravimetric energy density of 300 [Wh/kg] results in a capacity (C_{cell}) of 3,82 Ah. Furthermore, as for the instantaneous battery current, it is computed by means of equation (16), enabling to update step by step the SOC value through equation (17).

Once all the variables mentioned in this subsection are evaluated, the cost function can be evaluated at each iteration step thanks to equation (27).

Results

Herein, the results of the methodology are presented. Particularly, the results of an updated control strategy, which relies on high J, are presented via comparison with outcomes of [14] that depend on lower J. It is worth mentioning here that such an update is considered here to meet CH2E-SRIA's targets [15]. Afterwards, the idling and slew rate effects are included in the rule-based strategy and relative findings are first shown and then validated via benchmarking against DP.

Results Related to CH2E-SRIA Updated Target

In Figure 6, the comparison between the simulations at high ($1 \left[\frac{A}{cm^2}\right]$) and low ($0,3 \left[\frac{A}{cm^2}\right]$) current density are shown, without having been introduced yet the idling power. If the current density changes the same does the efficiency curve as shown in the Figure 3, so that it is necessary to get new control maps [20]. In Figure 6 (a), it is possible to observe the effect of changing the efficiency curve. The control strategy pursues the best efficiency, at the same power required, with the two different control maps obtained. Indeed, the updated efficiency curve, at high J, implies that the maximum efficiency corresponds to a lower dimensionless power value with respect to that with low J. Thus, the RB control strategy let the PEMFCS working, in the cruising phase (from about 1000 [s] to 7000 [s]), at lower power levels to minimize the fuel consumption at parity of P_{dem} . Consequently, the PEMFCS must be kept on for a longer time in case of maps obtained relying on high J (i.e., $1 \left[\frac{A}{cm^2}\right]$).

On the other hand, in Figure 6 (b) it is possible to visualize the battery SOC variation during the flight mission. In both cases there is a depletion till the SOC_t is reached, then SOC fluctuates around SOC_t itself in thermostatic-like fashion. Globally, the behaviour of the SOC is almost the same in the two cases analysed. The data presented in Figure 6 are schematically listed also in Table 2.

Figure 6. The figure shows the change in terms of (a) proton exchange membrane fuel cell system power (P_{PEMFCS}) and (b) state of charge of the battery (SOC), due to the update of the efficiency due to CH2E-SRIA [15].

Table 2. In the table there are data about the comparison between high ($1 \left[\frac{A}{cm^2}\right]$) and low ($0,3 \left[\frac{A}{cm^2}\right]$) current density efficiency curve. These data are obtained thanks to the tool in 14. *HHV-based; ** It is worth noting that hydrogen consumption is increased by 20% to account for reservoir mission (i.e., alternate and loiter phases).

B1DH79	High J	Low J
M_{H_2} [kg] (gross**)	36,20	32,26
FE [km/kg]	19,93	21,06
P_{batt} [kW]	1833	
$P_{PEMFCS,max}$ [kW]	500	
M_{batt} [kg]	1927	
M_{PEMFCS} [kg]	250	
$M_{H_2,tank}$ [kg]	241,33	216,07
Vol_{batt} [l]	696	
Vol_{PEMFCS} [l]	588,23	
$Vol_{H_2,tank}$ [l]	905	806,50
$C_{batt,tot}$ [kWh]	578	
SOC_{in} [-]	0,95	
SOC_{min} [-]	0,19	
SOC_{end} [-]		
E_{H_2} [kWh]*	1189	1060
$E_{consbatt}$ [kWh]	440	

(a)

Figure 7. The figure shows the percentages of masses (a) and volumes (b) of the $J = 1 \left[\frac{A}{cm^2} \right]$ case. Moreover, the mass and volume added to the powertrain are detailed, while giving information about their percentage distribution.

As it is possible to deduce from Table 2, for the same energy provided by the battery ($E_{consbatt}$), the energy coming from hydrogen is higher for high J scenario. This can be explained by the fact that when the P_{PEMFCS} reaches its maximum (500 [kW]), the efficiency is very low. This is reflected in an increment of M_{H_2} that passes from 32,26 to 36,20 [kg], thus reducing the FE. The latter parameter varies from 21,06 to 19,93 $\left[\frac{km}{kg} \right]$. The FE variation is the key effect resulting from updating control maps.

The analysis presented in this subsection is useful to assess the effectiveness of the upgraded control maps. Moreover, in Figure 7, total mass and volume values are reported, as well as the percentual impact of each system component and they are within the constraints in Table 1. Moreover, it is remarkable that even if only the 1 [%] of the overall mass is due to the fuel, the tank mass and volume impact for the 10 [%] and 41 [%], respectively.

DP Strategy Validation

In this Section, the proposed RB strategy is validated relying on DP routine. As discussed in previous sections, slew rate is necessary to avoid a step response of the PEMFCS during rapid load changing, while idling power allows for mitigating the failure mechanisms coming from the frequency of starts and stops. Moreover, in Figure 8 (a), a comparison between RB and DP is presented.

The DP routine keeps P_{PEMFCS} at a constant value (i.e., about 200 kW) during the cruising phase, to which a power demand of 162 [kW] is associated. Specifically, after the take-off, P_{PEMFCS} does not vary until reaching the landing phase. As for the RB strategy, during the cruising, some steps variations are present and P_{PEMFCS} fluctuates around 200 kW. Indeed, as showed in Figure 8 (a), it is 110 [kW]. Moreover, it is

evident that during take-off and landing the DP lets the PEMFCS working at a fluctuating power level. This shows the unattainable ideality of such a solution for what said in Control Strategy section about the mechanical stress.

In Figure 8 (b), η_{PEMFCS} is presented. Particularly, the behavior of efficiency is strictly linked to that one of the PEMFCS power along the time: when it reaches its minimum, η_{PEMFCS} reaches its maximum value and vice versa. Furthermore, Figure 8 (c) shows the comparison of SOC trajectories in the two cases, considering the same initial and final SOC. In Figure 8 (d), it is possible to see the recharging phase of the battery, which takes place during the cruise phase. In such moments, P_{batt} is negative, while P_{PEMFCS} is higher than P_{dem} .

The main difference between the two cases analyzed lies in the fact that DP outputs a more monotonic trend for battery SOC, which is beneficial for its state of health. However, from the viewpoint of the energy provided by the battery, it is the same between rule-based and DP since the trajectories are evaluated by assuming the same initial and final SOC. Based on this consideration, it is possible to compare coherently the energies consumed by the PEMFCS in DP and RB.

Figure 8. The figure shows the comparison between the DP and the RB (a) P_{PEMFC} , (b) η_{PEMFC} and (c) SOC of B. (d) Results of the dynamic programming simulation in terms of power that proton-exchange membrane fuel cell system and battery should provide to satisfy the load.

Table 3. In the table there are the data of the simulation relative to dynamic programming and rule-based control strategy (including the degradation aware energy management strategies i.e. PEMFCS power slew rate and idling, see the Control Strategy Section). *HHV-based; ** It is worth noting that hydrogen consumption is increased by 20% to account for reservoir mission (i.e., alternate and loiter phases).

B1DH79	RB	DP
M_{H_2} [kg] (gross**)	36,13	36
$M_{H_2,tank}$ [kg]	240,87	240,00
$Vol_{H_2,tank}$ [l]	905	902
SOC_{min} [-]	0,2	
SOC_{end} [-]		
E_{H_2} [kWh]*	1187	1182
$E_{consbatt}$ [kWh]	435	

Table 3 shows data about the DP and RB simulations. It must be pointed out that the values of P_{batt} , $P_{PEMFC,max}$, M_{batt} , M_{PEMFC} , Vol_{batt} , Vol_{PEMFC} , $C_{batt,tot}$ and SOC_{in} are the same of those in Table 2. In terms of M_{H_2} , the RB solution integrated with idling and rate limiter corrections, like the result in Table 2. This demonstrates that idling and slew rate do not exhibit a significant impact on fuel consumption. Comparing these results with those shown in Figure 7, no significant differences are visible. Indeed, the total mass is 2454,13 [kg] and total volume is 2187,72 [l]. This is because the DH analyzed is the same.

Conclusions

Starting from a model-based procedure enabling to size the electrical powertrain of a regional aircraft while also considering the hybridizing components energy management strategy, several novelties have been introduced in this work. It is remarkable that the model-based methodology analyzed is flexible since it relies on control maps that adapt themselves to the design selected for the hybrid aircraft. As a result, different degrees of hybridization can be explored.

The first novelty introduced concerns the proton-exchange membrane fuel cell system efficiency, which has been upgraded to match the

current state of the art targets. The new efficiency model reflects in the necessity of adjusting the control maps, through which the rule-based control strategy proposed is implemented. This way, the power split between aircraft electrical components can be properly determined considering the current technological scenario.

Moreover, idling and slew rate, applied to the power supplied by the fuel cell system, are introduced to account for the degradation. Therefore, the contribution of the present study lies in introducing some precautions, which are pivotal for preserving the state of health of the fuel cell system. In fact, through the adoption of the slew rate, a too rapid load changing for the fuel cell system is limited, while, by means of idling power, the frequent switching on and off of the system is avoided. Another original contribution of this study is the validation of the updated rule-based control strategy with dynamic programming routine widely used in automotive but rarely in aviation. The rule-based control strategy is more flexible than dynamic programming but through the latter, the proposed energy management strategy has been validated by comparing the results in terms of fuel consumption. A result remarkably close to the dynamic programming one is fulfilled: 36,13 [kg] of hydrogen consumed. Sure enough, the fuel consumption computed through dynamic programming is 36 [kg], just 0,13 [kg] lower. In other words, such findings allow declaring that a rule-based control strategy allows for the proper on-board energy management of such energy conversion systems. In this regard, a key aspect is that the proposed control strategy can be easily adapted to different scenarios. Regarding the latter aspect, it is worth recalling that the approach adopted in the present article aimed at high level preliminary design of a regional aircraft, thus leading to address the most suitable sizing strategies of the electrified part of the turbo-prop powertrain, considering the energy requirements and constraints about total mass and volume. As a further step, an optimization analysis may be conducted in such a way to deeply explore the design space, while ensuring minimum fuel consumption and the constraints on mass and volume. It may also be considered the fuel cell functioning at high temperature for its advantages in cooling demand. In the future, such an analysis could also include the economic aspects. Moreover, another point that can be deeply detailed in future works relates to the degradation aware design. In this sense, beginning-of-life versus end-of-life studies can be carried out, thanks to further tool adaptation, for guaranteeing that the fuel cell system is still able to supply the required power. This allows for a better understanding of the behavior of a fuel cell system under certain stress conditions.

References

1. Emissions from planes and ships: facts and figures, <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/headlines/society/20191129STO67756/emissions-from-planes-and-ships-facts-and-figures-infographic>, Accessed on February the 19th, 2025.
2. Our world in data, <https://ourworldindata.org/search?q=aviation%20emissions>, Accessed on February the 19th, 2025.
3. Bills, A, Sripad, S, Fredericks, WL, Singh, M., Viswanathan, V. *Performance Metrics Required of Next-Generation Batteries to Electrify Commercial Aircraft*. ACS Energy Letters Journal 2020;663–668.
4. Li, X., Wu, X. *Autonomous energy management strategy for a hybrid power system of more-electric aircraft based on composite droop schemes*. International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems, 129:106828, 2021.
5. Thirkell, A., Chen, R., and Harrington, I., "A Fuel Cell System Sizing Tool Based on Current Production Aircraft," SAE Technical Paper 2017-01-2135, 2017.

6. Inacio, G., Mourao, C., Castro, A., and Lacava, P., "Feasibility Study of Using Liquid Hydrogen Tanks as Energy Carriers and Cooling Agents for a Small Aircraft Powered by PEMFCs," SAE Technical Paper 2022-01-0009, 2022.
7. Mislav, A., Sergeant, A., D'Arpino, M., Ramesh, P., Canova, M., *Design space exploration of lithium-ion battery packs for hybrid-electric regional aircraft propulsion*, Journal of Propulsion and Power, Volume 39, pp. 390-403, 2023.
8. Palladino, V., Bartoli, N., Pommier-Budinger, V., Benard, E., Schmollgruber, P., Jordan, A., *Optimization of a hydrogen-based hybrid propulsion system under aircraft performance constraints*, Chinese Journal of Aeronautics, Volume 36, pp. 41-56, 2023.
9. Romeo, G., Borello, F., Correa, G. *Setup and test flights of all-electric two-seater aeroplane powered by fuel cells*. Journal of Aircraft 2011;48(4):1331–41.
10. Bayrak, Z.U., Kaya, U., Oksuztepe, E. *Investigation of PEMFC performance for cruising hybrid powered fixed-wing electric UAV in different temperatures*. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy 2020;45(11):7036–45.
11. HECATE, <https://hecate-project.eu/>, Accessed on February the 19th, 2025.
12. Kösters, T.L., von Schweinitz, A.G., Heere, M., Friedrichs, J., Gao, X. *Experimental study and simulations of hydrogen cooling effectiveness for aviation PEM fuel cells*, Scientific Reports, Volume 13, article no. 23016, 2023.
13. Hoenicke, P., Ghosh, D., Muhandes, A., Bhattacharya, S., Bauer, C., Kallo, J., et al. *Power management control and delivery module for a hybrid electric aircraft using fuel cell and battery*. Energy Conversion and Management 2021;244:114445.
14. Sparano, M., Sorrentino, M., Troiano, G., Cerino, G., Piscopo, G., Basaglia, M., Pianese, C. *The future technological potential of hydrogen fuel cell systems for aviation and preliminary co-design of a hybrid regional aircraft powertrain through a mathematical tool*. Energy Conversion and Management, Volume 281, article no. 116822, 2023.
15. Aliberti, P., Minneci, M., Sorrentino, M., Cuomo, F., & Musto, C. *Efficiency-Based Modeling of Aeronautical Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell Systems for Integrated Simulation Framework Applications*. Energies, 18(4), 999. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en18040999>, 2025.
16. Sundstrom, O. and Guzzella, L., *A Generic Dynamic Programming Matlab Function*. In 18th IEEE International Conference on Control Applications: part of 2009 IEEE Multi-conference on Systems and Control, Saint Petersburg, Russia, July 8-10, 2009.
17. Sorrentino, M., Pianese, C., Maiorino, M., *An integrated mathematical tool aimed at developing highly performing and cost-effective fuel cell hybrid vehicles*. Journal of Power Sources 2013;221:308–17.
18. Wang, B., Zhao, D., Li, W., Wang, Z., Huang, Y., You, Y., et al. *Current technologies and challenges of applying fuel cell hybrid propulsion systems in unmanned aerial vehicles*. Progress Aerospace Sciences 2020;116:100620.
19. Saxena, S., Floch, C.L., Macdonald, J., Moura, S. *Quantifying EV battery end-of-life through analysis of travel needs with vehicle powertrain models*. Journal of Power Sources 2015;282:265–76.
20. Sorrentino, M., Rizzo, G., Arsie, I., *Analysis of a rule-based control strategy for on-board energy management of series hybrid vehicles*, Control Engineering Practice, Volume 19, pp. 1433-1441, 2011.
21. Wallnofer-Ogris, E., Poimer, F., Koll, R., Macherhammer, M.G., Trattner A. "Main degradation mechanisms of polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell stacks – Mechanisms, influencing factors, consequences, and mitigation strategies", International Journal of hydrogen energy, Volume 50, pp. 1159-1182, 2024.
22. Xie, Z., Gao, J., and Zhou, S., "Research on Air Mass Flow and Pressure Control Method for the Multi-Stack Fuel Cell System Based on Model Predictive Control," SAE Technical Paper 2023-01-7037, 2023.
23. Gorla, N., *Analisi e modellazione delle prestazioni di uno stack PEM*, Master Thesis, Polytechnic University of Turin, Italy, 2022. <https://webthesis.biblio.polito.it/24909/1/tesi.pdf>, Accessed on February the 19th, 2025.
24. Finger, D.F., Braun, C., Bil, C. *Impact of battery performance on the initial sizing of hybrid-electric general aviation aircraft*. Journal of Aerospace Engineering 2020;33(3):04020007.
25. Hepperle, M., 'Electric Flight – Potential and Limitations', AVT-209 Workshop, Lisbon, 1–30, 2012, available at <https://elib.dlr.de/78726/1/MP-AVT-209-09.pdf>, Accessed on February the 19th, 2025.
26. ACAL Energy hydrogen fuel cell reaches conventional engine durability | GreenFleet, <https://greenfleet.net/news/28062013/acal-energy-hydrogen-fuel-cell-reaches-conventional-engine-durability>, Accessed on February the 19th, 2025.
27. Marx, N., Boulon, L., Gustin, F., Hissel, D., Agbossou, K. *A review of multi-stack and modular fuel cell systems: Interests, application areas and on-going research activities*. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy 2014;39(25):12101–11.
28. Bensadoun, E., *Hydrogen Storage on board aeroplane and ground infrastructure ground infrastructure: Air Liquide Advanced Technologies*. Workshop on aeronautical applications of fuel cell and hydrogen technologies, Lampoldshausen, 2015, available at https://www.fch.europa.eu/sites/default/files/12.%20Bensadoun%20%28ID%202844157%29_0.pdf, Accessed on October the 19th, 2023.
29. Arsie, I., Graziosi, M., Pianese, C., Rizzo, G., Sorrentino, M. *Control strategy optimization for hybrid electric vehicles via provisional load estimate*. Review of Automotive Engineering, 26:341-348, 2005.
30. SLBATT (2020), <https://www.lithium-battery-factory.com/it/discharge-rate/>, Accessed on February the 19th 2025.

Contact Information

Contact details for the main author should be included here. Details may include mailing address, email address, and/or telephone number (whichever is deemed appropriate).

Acknowledgments

Funded by the European Union under GA no 101101961 - HECATE. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The project is supported by the Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking and its Members.

Definitions/Abbreviations

Abbreviations

PEMFCs Proton-exchange membrane fuel cell system

FAA	Federal Aviation Administration	$G [-]$	Penalty function
B	Battery	$HHV_{H_2} [MJ/kg]$	Hydrogen higher heating value
SOC	State of charge	$I_{b,cell,max} [A]$	Maximum battery single cell current
DP	Dynamic programming	$I_{dischg/chg} [A]$	Charging/discharging battery single cell current
FE	Fuel economy	$I_{b,cell} [A]$	Battery single cell current
SR	Slew rate	$M_{H_2} [kg]$	Hydrogen consumed mass
RB	Rule based	$M_{tot} [kg]$	Total powertrain mass
DH	Degree of hybridization	$M_{batt} [kg]$	Battery mass
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicles	$M_{PEMFCs} [kg]$	Proton-exchange membrane fuel cell system mass
TE	Thermal engine	$M_{H_2 tank} [kg]$	Hydrogen tank mass
Greek Symbols		$m_{B,cell} [kg]$	Battery single cell mass
$\eta_{batt} [-]$	Battery efficiency	$m_{uPEMFCs} [kg/kW]$	Proton-exchange membrane fuel cell system unit mass
$\eta_{PEMFCs} [-]$	Proton-exchange fuel cell system efficiency	$m_{u,tank} [kg_{H_2}/kg_{tank}]$	Hydrogen tank unit mass
Symbols		$\dot{m}_{H_2} [kg/s]$	Hydrogen mass flow rate
$C_{batt,tot} [kWh]$	Battery capacity	$N_{BC} [-]$	Number of battery cell
$C_{cell} [Ah]$	Battery single cell capacity	$J [A/cm^2]$	Density current
$C_{rate} [1/h]$	Coulombic rate	$P_{idl} [kW]$	Idling fuel cell system power
$D [km]$	Distance	$P_{batt,cell} [kW]$	Battery single cell power
$D_{PEMFCs,EOL} [%]$	Degradation at end of life of the fuel cell system	$P_{stack} [kW]$	Fuel cell stack power
$E_{H_2} [kWh]$	Energy consumed by the fuel cell system	$\bar{P}_m [kW]$	Average power demand
$E_{consbatt} [kWh]$	Energy consumed by the battery	$P_{aux} [kW]$	Auxiliary fuel cell system power

$P_{idl} [kW]$	Idling fuel cell system power	$vol_{PEMFCs} [kW/l]$	Proton-exchange membrane fuel cell system unit volume
$P_{batt,cell} [kW]$	Battery single cell power	$vol_{tank} [kg_{H_2}/L_{tank}]$	Hydrogen tank unit volume
$Q_{tot} [Ah]$	Nominal battery capacity	$Vol_{tot} [l]$	Total powertrain volume
$R_{in} [m\Omega]$	Battery internal resistance	$Vol_{batt} [l]$	Battery volume
$R_{in,cell} [m\Omega]$	Battery single cell internal resistance	$Vol_{PEMFCs} [l]$	Proton-exchange membrane fuel cell system volume
$R_{chg} [m\Omega]$	Battery charging resistance	$Vol_{H_2tank} [l]$	Hydrogen tank volume
$R_{dischg} [m\Omega]$	Battery discharging resistance	$Vol_{cell} [l]$	Battery single cell volume
$SOC_t [-]$	Target battery state of charge	$x(t) [-]$	State variable in dynamic programming
$SOC_{end} [-]$	Final battery state of charge	$x_{f,min} [-]$	Minimum final state variable in dynamic programming
$SOC_{min} [-]$	Minimum battery state of charge	$x_{f,max} [-]$	Maximum final state variable in dynamic programming
$SOC_f [-]$	Final battery state of charge	$\Delta t_{PEMFCs-OFF} [s]$	Fuel cell system switching off time
$t [s]$	Time	$\Delta SOC [\%]$	Battery state of charge variation
$t_f [s]$	Final mission time		
$u(t)$	Control variable dynamic programming		
$V_{batt,cell} [V]$	Battery single cell voltage		